

	<p>Development of a protocol for biometric-based animal tracking and tracing</p>	

State-of-the-art of Livestock Movement Monitoring Using Computer Vision Systems

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Livestock production today is no longer limited to obtaining economic goals. Modern society is concerned about food safety and quality, efficient and sustainable animal farming, healthy animals and acceptable environmental impact of livestock production (Parsons et al., 2007; Frost et al., 2003). As a consequence, there is a growing need to monitor many variables during the entire production process in order to satisfy these targets. Traditionally, livestock management decisions have been based almost entirely on the judgment and experience of the stockman who has to estimate or guess the likely effects of any controlled action, taking into account the complexities of the processes involved. Today, automated monitoring and controlling techniques are becoming more important to support the farmer in managing the production process (Frost et al., 2003). Although biological processes involving living organisms have always been considered as too complex to be monitored and controlled in an automated way, today new emerging technologies offer possibilities to develop full automated on-line monitoring and control of many of these processes. As Berckmans (2004) points out, one of the objectives of Precision Livestock Farming in the field of monitoring, is to develop *on-line tools to monitor farm animals continuously during their life*, in an automated way, with objective measures and criteria calculated on-line from collected data and without imposing additional stress to the animals.

Computer-controlled systems for the remote monitoring of livestock have the potential to increase production, efficiency and improve animal health and welfare (Frost et al., 1997; Van der Stuyft et al., 1991). Some applications in pig husbandry for computer controlled systems were first suggested by DeShazer et al. (1988) and Schofield (1990) and included recording animal weight, growth rate, fatness and conformation (external body shape), control of diet, monitoring behavioural vices and providing management decision support. Of these, *estimation of pig weight* was identified as a primary application for the

development of image analysis techniques for use in livestock production. Improving the stockman's knowledge of pig weight and growth rate is a vital aid to the maintenance of health and maximum production efficiency. Several approaches for *locating pigs in images* have been reported since. While Tillet (1991) used a training image and an assumption of smooth bending along the animal's back, Marchant and Schofield (1993) used a 'snake' algorithm to locate the edges of a pig at a drinker. The snake algorithm was good at locating smooth continuous edges in an image but it is difficult to include prior knowledge of the overall shape required. In Denmark, Brandl and Jorgensen (1996) monitored the growth of over 400 pigs, but their analysis was performed off-line using a manual technique for detecting the pig outline. Marchant et al. (1999) introduced fully automated algorithms which find the plan view outline of pigs while they are at a feeding station (Fig. 1). Their algorithm divides the outline into major body components and measures accurately defined areas and dimensions for each pig as it grows. Also, they present a method of camera calibration which allows for changes in camera positioning and lens arrangement. Later, Schofield et al. (1999) devised a prototype hardware and software system that could successfully estimate the growth rates of pigs (Fig. 2) and had the ability to work unattended in a piggery environment.

Figure 1. Outline of pig area obtained from image analysis showing major body components used for weight estimation (Taken from Marchant et al., 1999)

Figure 2. Daily medians for Large White pigs and fitted line (Taken from Schofield et al., 1999)

However, apart from growth rate estimation using computer vision, the patterns of movement of animals could be used to indicate the status of their health and wellbeing. Thus, McFarlane and Schofield (1995) developed an algorithm for the segmentation and *tracking of piglets* and tested it on a 200-image sequence of 10 piglets moving on a straw background. The image-capture rate was 1 image/140 ms. The segmentation method was a combination of image differencing with respect to a median background and a Laplacian operator. The features tracked were blob edges in the segmented image. During tracking, the piglets were modelled as ellipses initialised on the blobs. Each piglet was tracked by searching for blob edges in an elliptical window about the piglet's position, which was predicted from its previous two positions. Model-based image processing allows a target object to be found even when there is only partial information about the object. Based on a point distribution model which learns from a training set of data (shapes), Marchant and Onyango (1995) showed that this trained model can be fit to an image using grey level shading information and edge strengths. They could fit the model to single images in a range of conditions including multiple pigs partially obscuring each other. Such a technique has particular potential for poultry movement tracking, where occlusion would be a very common occurrence. Later, Onyango et al. (1995) enhanced the previous model by adding an automated method for its initialisation using the position and orientation of ridges in the grey level landscape. An algorithm for tracking movement through sequences of images, where a single pig is viewed from above, was proposed by

Tillett et al. (1997). Their point distribution approach modelled position and rotation as well as more subtle motion such as bending and head nodding (Fig. 3). This type of model-based tracking could be used to characterise animal behaviour over time.

Figure 3. Position in sequence (for x and y coordinates) produced by the point distribution model used to track movement of an individual pig (Tillett et al., 1997)

A mobile imaging system for live pig weight estimation was developed by Rydberg et al. (2004). The system comprises lights, a camera and a computer positioned on a handcart, which is intended to be moved forwards by the farmer during the inspection walk. The contour of the pig is detected automatically by the image analysis system excluding the head from further processing. The system is believed to be capable to estimate the weight of more than 400 pigs per hour. A case specific study aiming to predict the carcass composition from body dimensions of living pigs by way of an image analysis system was conducted by Doeschl-Wilson et al. (2005). In vivo image measurements were established to be useful to estimate muscle size, carcass conformation as well as carcass composition, each of these features being significantly important in pig production. A recent investigation accomplished by Parsons et al. (2007) dealt with the matter of real time control of pig growth through an integrated management system. This research aimed to test the principles of model optimisation and the control of growth by way of integrated management systems. The growth obtained from image analysis was comparable to a mechanistic model that estimates growth from a series of variables such as current status, growth potential, feed intake and environment of the pig.

Monitoring broiler chickens in a large production house is a challenging task. Chickens tend to move in a somewhat sporadic manner, and include sporadic walking, feeding and drinking interspersed by resting and less frequent activities including dust bathing, stretching and peer-interaction (Appleby et al., 1989). The large size of commercial broiler houses adds to this challenge, as such houses may typically accommodate 20 000 birds with up to 20 birds/m². It is well documented that the locomotion of the chickens is an indicator of health and welfare (Appleby et al., 1989). A first approach of *computer visual tracking of poultry* was given by Sergeant et al. (1998). By means of segmentation and separation to produce centroids of each broiler chicken per frame (Fig. 4), from images taken by a single video camera mounted above a population of 13 broilers, they tracked the birds and showed their interaction with the drinker and feeder. Although they were able to monitor individual movement, the system still needs further development to address the large numbers of broiler chickens in a production house, and the integration of views from multiple cameras.

Figure 4. Binary image showing broiler chickens (13) segmented by region-based hysteresis (Taken from Sergeant et al., 1998)

Sex separation of baby chicks is still mostly done by hand. Typically, workers are positioned around chick sexing tables to observe and sort the males from the females by differences in wing feathers. For typical operations hatching 250 000 to 500 000 baby chicks a day, a crew about ten to thirty people must be involved in chick sexing. However, the advantages of chick sexing in the broiler industry are numerous: (i) enhanced feeding efficiency (growing and harvesting male and female broiler chickens differently enables better management for optimum results); (ii) improved debone meat production (harvesting deboned meats by using large male broilers provides increased

benefits at the market place); and (iii) processing line efficiency (with reduced variation of large and small bird sizes, the equipment may be more precisely adjusted to achieve greater performance. The equipment can handle more uniform sized birds for enhanced yield, efficiency and productivity). To this point, technologies using machine vision enabling automated chick sex sorting operations have great potential. By using digital video cameras, automated mechanics and computer image processing systems, an automated system can inspect chicks at high speed. Tao and Walker (2002) patented an automated method for feather sexing of poultry chicks using ultraviolet imaging (Fig. 5). They explained that under regular lighting, the colour intensity of down and feather of baby chicks are essentially the same and it is difficult to separate the feathers in the image. However, by using UV light, their optimal system significantly enhanced the feathers by suppressing the downs in images, producing clearer feather signals for subsequent identification and segmentation of feathers in the image. The digital video camera captures a clear image of chick wings using selected light wavelengths from 250 to 450 nm. Special lighting architecture provides maximum illumination enhancement for the camera and best feature extraction for the pattern recognition software. Misclassification errors ranging from 2-6% were found with their method.

Figure 5. Schematic of automated feather sexing of poultry chicks using ultraviolet imaging system (Taken from Tao and Walker, 2002)

The broiler chicken producer uses body weight data to collect valuable information about growth rate and weight uniformity of the chickens, feed conversion efficiency, occurrence of disease problems and vitality (Flood et al., 1992). Traditional methods for check weighing generally involve the simple procedure of penning a group of birds, catching them and weighing them singly or in groups. To obtain a good representation of the body weights of the flock, careful attention must be given to the size and distribution of the sample of birds drawn for weighing. At least 1 % should be weighed and these birds must be taken equally from every pen in the house or from every block of cages (Anonymous, 1982). When large numbers of chicken weights are obtained, this conventional method is labour-intensive, stressful to birds, and injuries can occur especially when heavier broilers are weighed.

De Wet et al. (2003) detailed an alternative procedure to estimate *broiler chicken live weight* directly from its dimensions *by means of image analysis techniques* (Fig. 6). With their method, they showed that the relative error in weigh estimation from image surface data was 10%. To reduce this error, these researchers conjecture that the use of polarization filters on the light sources and camera to cut out specular reflections should be adopted. A camera at a sufficient height – 1 m above the floor, can cover approximately 5 m² of the floor in one image. With an average occupation of 16 birds per m², this translates into 80 birds in one image. So, in a flock of 10 000 birds, two cameras at opposite corners of the pen could be sufficient to obtain a truly representative picture of the body weights of the flock (De Wet et al., 2003). Vranken et al. (2005) improved the accuracy of automatic broiler weighing by image analysis. In combining automatic weighing platforms with an image analysis system, a method aiming to improve the assessment of the average body weight of a group of broilers was developed. The relation between actual weight and the area of animals was used to estimate body weight. The method was investigated during three fattening periods in three different experimental broiler houses. It was further evaluated against frequent manual weighing and was found to provide an enhanced estimation of the actual average body weight.

Figure 6. Relationship between chicken weight and surface area pixel ($r=0.98$) (Taken from De Wet et al., 2003)

Leroy et al. (2003; 2005) developed a system to monitor fully automatically the *activities of laying hens to score their welfare* and to use this information for better managing the production process environment. Behavioural characteristics of laying hens are usually evaluated by audio-visual observation done by the farmer. This method is time-consuming expensive and cannot be done continuously during the life time of the animal. Automated objective surveillance by means of cameras and image processing techniques has the ability to generate data providing a continuous measure of behaviour, without disturbing the animals. An automated on-line image processing technique was developed by Leroy et al. (2003) to quantify the behaviour of laying hens. The first implementation of the system allowed identifying three types of behaviour (standing, walking and scratching). Later, these researchers improved their measures of trajectory and rotation of an individual laying hen so as to recognise six different behaviour phenotypes (standing, sitting, sleeping, grooming, scratching, pecking). This new system was tested on a set of over 14000 video fragments of a single hen in a cage, each fragment containing one of the six behavior types. The average classification rate was between 70% - 96%, except 21% for pecking, due to an unreliable tracking of the chicken's head. Best results were obtained for sleeping (96%) and standing (90%).

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